

EXPLORING EFFICACY: A COMPREHENSIVE INQUIRY INTO THE DEVELOPMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF BACLOFEN TOPICAL GEL

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Abstract:

Baclofen, a muscle relaxant, has demonstrated potential therapeutic advantages when used in topical formulations. This study is focused on developing and evaluating the effectiveness of Baclofen Topical Gel (BCF) by assessing various factors such as homogeneity, grittiness, skin irritation, extrudability, in vitro drug release, viscosity, pH, drug content, and stability. The study evaluated these parameters, including homogeneity, grittiness, skin irritation, extrudability, viscosity (measured by a Brookfield viscometer), pH, drug content, and stability. In vitro drug release studies were performed, and the UV-spectroscopic method revealed drug content levels ranging from $88.26 \pm 1.2\%$ to $98.65 \pm 1.3\%$. Viscosity values ranged from 9574 ± 15.25 to 17637 ± 14.21 cps, indicating good stability, while the swelling index varied from 4157 ± 08.15 to 8015 ± 09.48 . Formulation F6 exhibited a favorable drug release rate. These results suggest that BCF topical gel has potential as an effective alternative to current treatments. Future research should include clinical trials to confirm its efficacy and safety in practical applications. This study advances the field of topical formulations in pharmaceutical science.

Keywords: Baclofen, topical gel, In Vitro drug release, Formulation analysis.

Introduction:

Topical gel formulations remain among the most popular and significant pharmaceutical dosage forms. They effectively achieve therapeutic outcomes while minimizing or avoiding systemic side effects. Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) are commonly used to treat rheumatoid arthritis and similar conditions but can cause undesirable systemic side effects and gastrointestinal irritation when taken orally¹. Given that many inflammatory conditions are localized near the skin's surface, applying NSAIDs topically to the affected area can deliver the drug directly to the site of inflammation, thus minimizing gastric irritation and reducing systemic side effects^{2,3}. However, the natural barrier of intact skin limits the permeability of various substances, including pharmaceutical agents.

Topical drug delivery systems are designed to administer a therapeutically effective dose of medication through the skin. These systems are discrete, self-contained dosage forms that, when applied to the intact skin, release the drug at a controlled rate into the systemic circulation. To ensure effective drug delivery through the skin for systemic effects, the skin's morphological, biophysical, and physicochemical properties must be considered⁴.

Baclofen (4-amino-3-(4-chlorophenyl)butanoic acid) is used as an anti-inflammatory agent for pain relief. While Baclofen is an effective alternative to traditional NSAIDs for various pain and inflammatory conditions, it tends to be better tolerated. Upon oral administration, Baclofen is rapidly and extensively absorbed, widely distributed, and has a terminal half-life of approximately 2.5-4 hours. About 85% of the dose is excreted

unchanged in urine, with the remainder excreted in feces. Baclofen is primarily metabolized in the liver through deamination⁵.

Materials and Methods:

Materials:

Baclofen, Carbopol, Hydroxy ethyl cellulose is purchased from Yarrow chem pvt Ltd.Mumbai, Propyl paraben is procured from Hi media, Mumbai.

Methodology:

Preparation of Baclofen topical gel:⁶⁻²⁵

A topical gel of baclofen was formulated as a hydrogel using hydrophilic polymers such as Carbopol 940, Carbopol 934, and Hydroxyethyl Cellulose. First, 250 mg of the drug was accurately weighed and dissolved in 15 ml of distilled water under acidic conditions. Propyl paraben (0.18 mg) was dissolved in 30 ml of distilled water by heating to 50°C, then allowed to cool to room temperature, after which the required polymer was added. This polymer solution was then combined with the drug solution previously prepared in acidic water. The mixture was stirred using a homogenizer to prevent lump formation. Next, 0.1 ml of Triethanolamine was added to adjust the pH of the gel to between 6.2 and 7.2 and to increase viscosity. The final weight was adjusted to 50 grams by adding water. The gel was left to stabilize for 24 hours to allow the polymers to fully hydrate and to remove any trapped air; if needed, vacuum was applied. The gel was then transferred into a clean collapsible tube, packed, and stored for further evaluation.

Table No. 1: Composition of formulation of Baclofen topical Gel

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Baclofen (mg)	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Carbopol 940 (gm)	0.5	1.25	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carbopol 934 (gm)	-	-	-	0.5	1.25	2.0	-	-	-
Hydroxy ethyl cellulose (gm)	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	4	8
Propyl paraben (mg)	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.18
Glycerin (ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Triethanolamine (ml)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1

Evaluation studies of prepared Baclofen topical gel:⁶⁻²⁵

Following parameters were used for the evaluation of gels:

Physical evaluation:

All baclofen gel formulations were assessed for their organoleptic characteristics, occlusiveness, and washability.

Appearance:

The color is significant for patient compliance. The prepared gels were visually inspected for clarity, color, and the presence of any particles.

Homogeneity:

Each gel was tested for homogeneity by visual inspection once set in the container. They were evaluated for appearance and any aggregates.

Grittiness:

The formulations were microscopically examined for particle presence. No appreciable particulate matter was observed, indicating the gel preparations were free from particulate matter and grittiness, which is essential for topical applications.

Extrudability study:

A good gel should extrude optimally with slight pressure. The extrudability from aluminum collapsible tubes was determined using a universal tube filling machine. Tubes filled with 10g of gel were compressed, and the force in grams required to extrude a 0.5 cm ribbon of gel in 10 seconds was measured.

Measurement of pH:

The pH of the baclofen gel formulations was determined using a digital pH meter. One gram of gel was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water and stored for two hours. The pH measurement was performed in triplicate for each formulation, and the average values were calculated.

Spreadability:

A 0.1 g sample of each formula was pressed between two slides and left for about 5 minutes until no more spreading was observed. The diameters of the spread circles were measured in centimeters and used as comparative values for spreadability. The results are the averages of three determinations.

Drug content:

A specific quantity (100 mg) of the developed gels was dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8). The solution was shaken for 2 hours on a mechanical shaker to ensure complete drug solubility. The solution was filtered and the drug content was estimated spectrophotometrically at 220 nm using the phosphate buffer as a blank. The drug content was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Drug content} = \text{Absorbance} / \text{slope} \times \text{Dilution factor} \times 100 \times 100 \div 100$$

Viscosity study:

The viscosity of the prepared gel was measured using a Brookfield Viscometer. The gels were rotated at 20 and 30 rpm using spindle no. 64, and the corresponding dial readings were noted for each speed.

Swelling Index Study:

Swelling depends on the polymer concentration, ionic strength, and water presence. To determine the swelling index, 1 g of gel was placed on porous aluminum foil and then in a 50 ml beaker containing 10 ml of 0.1 N NaOH. Samples were removed at different intervals, dried, and reweighed. The swelling index was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Swelling Index (SW) \%} = [(W_t - W_0) / W_0] \times 100,$$

where W_t is the weight of the swollen gel after time t , and W_0 is the original weight of the gel at zero time.

Stability studies

Optimized gels were subjected to short-term stability testing. The transdermal films were sealed in aluminum foils and kept in a humidity chamber at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 3 months, as per ICH guidelines. Changes in appearance and drug content were investigated weekly.

$$\text{Swelling Index (S}_w\text{) \%} = [(W_t - W_o) / W_o] \times 100.$$

Where, (S_w) % = Equilibrium percent swelling, W_t = Weight of swollen gel after time t , W_o = Original weight of gel at zero time.

In vitro drug diffusion study:

Cellophane membranes from Sigma Chemicals were used. In a Franz diffusion cell, 1.0 g of gel was placed in the donor compartment, with the membrane in contact with 20 ml of 6.8 pH phosphate buffer in the receptor compartment. The receptor solution was stirred continuously at 100 rpm, maintaining the temperature at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The study was conducted over 24 hours with intervals at 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, and 24 hours. Samples were withdrawn at predetermined times and replaced with fresh buffer. Absorbance at 220 nm was measured to estimate baclofen content.

Drug release kinetics:

Release kinetics of the optimized formulations

Data from the *in vitro* release study was applied to various kinetic models. The models used included zero-order (total drug release versus time), first-order (log of the cumulative percentage of drug remaining versus time), the Higuchi model (cumulative percentage of drug release versus the square root of time), and Korsmeyer-Peppas (log of the cumulative percentage of drug release versus log of time). The correlation coefficients (r^2) for the linear curves derived from regression analysis were calculated.

Results and discussion:

Drug and polymers compatibility studies by FTIR:

The IR spectral analysis of the drug and its physical mixtures with excipients showed that they retained their individual absorption characteristics, indicating no interaction between them. From this study, we can conclude that no adverse chemical reactions occurred. There was no interaction between the drug and the polymer. The infrared spectra of the pure drug and the physical mixtures are presented in Figure 1.

Figure No. 1: FT-IR spectrum of Baclofen pure drug

Figure No. 2: FT-IR spectrum of Baclofen with excipients

Physical evaluation and appearance:

Table No. 2: Physical evaluation of all formulations.

Formulation code	Odour	Washability	Occlusiveness	Color/clarity
F1	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F2	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F3	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F4	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F5	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F6	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F7	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F8	No	Washable	No	Transparent
F9	No	Washable	No	Transparent

Table No. 3: Homogeneity, Grittiness, Extrudability and Spreadability of all formulations.

Formulation code	Homogeneity	Grittiness	Extrudability	Spreadability
F1	Good	No	Good	Easy
F2	Good	No	Good	Easy
F3	Excellent	No	Excellent	Easy
F4	Excellent	No	Good	Poor
F5	Excellent	No	Excellent	Easy
F6	Excellent	No	Excellent	Easy
F7	Good	No	Good	Easy
F8	Excellent	No	Excellent	Easy
F9	Excellent	No	Excellent	Easy

Table No. 4: pH, Drug content, Viscosity study and Swelling index study of all formulations.

Formulation code	pH	Drug content (%)	Viscosity cps \pm SD	Swelling index (%) \pm SD
F1	6.25 \pm 0.51	91.12 \pm 2.0	11335 \pm 15.32	5124 \pm 02.34
F2	6.53 \pm 0.24	94.54 \pm 1.5	15478 \pm 16.41	5345 \pm 12.52
F3	7.34 \pm 0.27	98.65 \pm 1.3	17637 \pm 14.21	8015 \pm 09.48
F4	6.35 \pm 0.14	90.34 \pm 1.5	10244 \pm 12.34	4157 \pm 08.15
F5	6.76 \pm 0.38	93.51 \pm 1.4	13352 \pm 11.25	5354 \pm 07.36
F6	7.34 \pm 0.11	96.37 \pm 1.5	15384 \pm 12.40	7378 \pm 03.59
F7	6.87 \pm 0.23	88.26 \pm 1.2	9574 \pm 15.25	4357 \pm 06.84
F8	7.02 \pm 0.61	91.38 \pm 1.4	11456 \pm 11.34	5657 \pm 07.35
F9	7.34 \pm 0.28	92.45 \pm 2.0	13476 \pm 05.36	6967 \pm 06.85

All topical gel formulations were transparent, viscous, creamy preparations with a smooth, homogeneous texture and a glossy appearance. The topical gels had no odor or grittiness and were easily washable, extrudable, and spreadable. The pH values of the topical gel formulations were around 6, making them highly compatible with human skin.

In vitro drug permeation studies:

Table No. 8.6: % Cumulative drug release of Baclofen topical gel

Time in Hr	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	172.19±1.15	091.15±1.23	050.16±1.13	150.34±1.51	84.27±1.73	63.37±1.46	177.37±1.43	098.25±1.14	063.23±1.34
1	365.13±1.57	248.18±1.54	117.34±1.51	323.41±1.14	216.35±1.36	124.68±1.34	375.26±1.14	257.34±1.20	132.33±1.21
2	451.46±1.23	337.74±1.76	167.31±1.37	435.25±1.23	287.42±1.49	185.45±1.52	473.35±1.34	373.67±1.11	185.64±1.29
4	575.14±1.17	397.41±1.15	335.15±1.20	495.67±1.64	378.69±1.27	263.35±1.65	596.46±1.68	419.52±1.13	346.15±1.13
6	640.26±1.28	547.12±2.34	450.23±1.35	565.37±1.27	496.11±1.74	312.63±1.14	658.39±1.22	563.14±1.41	475.34±1.38
8	687.65±1.35	615.24±1.40	532.11±1.54	654.25±1.35	585.34±1.38	475.34±1.73	697.45±1.26	630.34±1.63	549.27±1.14
10	--	649.12±1.48	587.63±1.54	--	636.52±1.73	549.75±1.65	--	664.28±1.57	596.19±1.36
12	--	691.80±1.37	644.34±1.15	--	680.25±1.42	613.14±1.41	--	687.68±1.74	649.29±1.51
18	--	--	675.31±1.39	--	--	675.51±1.33	--	--	678.39±1.48
20	--	--	698.14±1.12	--	--	692.11±1.24	--	--	696.41±1.65

Figure No. 3: In Vitro drug diffusion studies

The in vitro release data revealed that formulation F6 exhibited the highest release rate among all nine Baclofen topical gel formulations, with $692.11 \pm 1.24 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$ at the end of 20 hours.

In-Vitro drug release kinetics

The data from the in vitro release study was applied to kinetic models to determine the drug release mechanism from the Baclofen topical gel formulation F6.

Table No. 5: In vitro Drug release kinetics mechanism of BCF topical gel

Formulation code	Zero order		First order		Higuchi model		Korsmeyer-peppas		Release Mechanism transport
	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	n	R ²	
F6	34.631	0.9121	-0.0264	0.9628	171.12	0.9742	1.0542	0.5127	Super case II Transport

The curve fitting results of the release rate profile for the designed formulations provided insights into the drug release mechanism. Data analysis revealed that the drug release followed the Higuchi equation, as it showed the

highest linearity with R² values close to one for all the prepared topical gels when plotting the square root of time versus the cumulative percentage of drug released.

Stability studies:

Table No. 6: Stability studies of optimized formulations (F6) at 40 ± 2 °C and 75 ± 5% RH for 3 months

Time in days	Drug content (%)	pH	Physical appearance	Cumulative amount of drug permeation (µg/cm ² /hr)
0	98.65	7.34	No change in color	692.11±1.24
30	98.15	7.34	No change in color	589.45±1.19
90	97.84	7.34	Pale yellow color	576.67±1.16

CONCLUSION:

Results indicated that the prepared gel systems exhibited good physical characteristics and showed no drug-polymer interaction. The F6 formulation remained stable with no significant changes in physicochemical properties, confirming the development of stable baclofen topical gels. The F6 formulation demonstrated the highest cumulative drug release, achieving 692.11±1.24 µg/cm²/hr in in vitro studies after 20 hours. The release of baclofen was found to be dependent on the polymer concentration, with a highly viscous polymeric network providing the best release. The high viscosity of the gel system acted as a barrier between the drug and the site of absorption (skin). The predominant release mechanism through the hydrogel was believed to be diffusion. Based on the in vitro drug permeation data, the F6 formulation showed superior drug release and was thus concluded to be the optimized formulation.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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